

Artificial Intelligence for Education: Adjusting Qualitative Research Data Analysis to the Needs of the *Digital Natives*

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Abstract

This IRB-approved qualitative case study grounded in Vygotsky's socio-cultural constructivism theory was conducted with 14 International students at a North-eastern public university. The research question was concerned with the degree to which the participants found the addition of technology helpful for their reading comprehension. The data were collected via interviews, surveys, participant and site observations, and notes. This study found that all the subjects stated they strongly benefitted from the addition of the means of technology. The paper behind this presentation is concerned with the topics regarding the possible usage of the means of artificial intelligence in service of educational needs of graduate students and faculty at the higher education establishments. Among the available nowadays tools are such programs as AlphaSense, MAXQDA, NVivo, to name just a few. In particular, the author focuses on demonstration of the results of the qualitative research data analysis of the subjects' interviews with the help of such software as MAXQDA and MAXQDA Plus. The benefits from utilization of this digital program to the young and beginning researchers in the diverse fields of education significantly outweigh the ones from the traditional ways to code and analyze the data manually. The educational researchers born in the era of global computerization are often referred to as *digital Natives*, as these young generations of learners have grown up habitually using and giving strong preference to the digital means of acquiring and storing information, for communication, and daily research for personal, professional, and educational needs. Upon gaining the knowledge from this paper and presentation, the conference audiences might consider incorporating teaching and utilizing the discussed software in their high school or college/university research classes' curricula.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, digital Natives; graduate students; MAXQDA, qualitative data analysis